

Towards Climate-Resilient Cities: Digital Twins and Nature-based Solutions for Urban Heat Mitigation Planning

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Abstract. This research explores using Destination Earth (DestinE) services as a digital twin framework to model and analyze Urban Heat Island (UHI) effects at the city level in extreme climate contexts. Focusing on Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, alongside neighborhoods in Jeddah and Dhahran/Dammam for comparative analysis, the study integrates diverse data sources and machine learning techniques to simulate UHI patterns and assess nature-based solutions for urban cooling. The framework combines DestinE's computational power and FAIR data principles to enable scenario testing through direct integration or local deployment within city-managed digital twins. This approach aims to support urban planners and decision-makers with scalable, data-driven insights to enhance climate resilience in rapidly urbanizing, heat-stressed cities.

Keywords: Digital Twin, Urban Heat Island (UHI), Nature-based Solutions (NbS), Machine Learning, Climate Resilience.

1. Introduction

This research explores the application of Destination Earth (DestinE [1]) services as a digital twin framework to model and analyze urban heat island effects at the city level within an extreme climate context.

The urban heat island effect, in which cities experience elevated temperatures compared to their surrounding areas, poses a critical challenge amid the pressures of climate change. To address this, we propose a city-scale digital twin as a data-driven framework to simulate the formation and evolution of UHI patterns. Leveraging the European Commission's Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative, this digital twin enables the systematic evaluation of nature-based solutions for urban cooling, offering a pathway toward sustainable and resilient urban climate adaptation.

The digital twin enables planners to model and assess the effectiveness of NbS, such as urban greening, green roofs, and permeable surfaces, in mitigating UHI hotspots.

Preliminary results suggest that targeted NbS can reduce surface temperatures by a significant margin. By using the digital twin, cities can identify the most effective scenarios for their specific urban environments, supporting data-driven climate resilience planning. The digital twin enables visualization of urban heat islands and assessment of the effectiveness of urban interventions in mitigating them.

The DestinE platform is planned to provide the foundational infrastructure for this work, including a federated data ecosystem and high-performance computing capabilities. It enables the integration of diverse data sources at fine spatiotemporal resolutions and the execution of complex simulations. This framework demonstrates the practical value of DestinE in sustainable urban development.

2. Methodology

The research employs a city-scale digital twin framework to model and analyze urban heat island effects. This approach integrates multiple data sources to create a dynamic, virtual replica of the urban environment. The Destination Earth (DestinE) platform provides the foundational infrastructure for this work, leveraging its high-performance computing (HPC) environment and federated data ecosystem. This aligns the framework with F.A.I.R. data principles [2, 3], allowing a city to either connect directly to DestinE services or integrate the model locally.

The methodology is based on a detailed functional architecture, as illustrated in the provided figure (Figure 1). The diagram illustrates several stages of data processing:

- **Data Acquisitions:** How data is gathered from environmental sensors and infrastructure systems, e.g. sourcing from local, municipal and other government data repositories.
- **Ingestion:** The process of bringing this data into the system, including data cleaning and data management (includes classification and versioning), and geospatial data storage.
- **Digital Twin Core:** The central hub where the "Model Creator and Simulation" are staged. This is where the 3D urban morphology and other data are integrated to create a virtual replica and enable predictive analytics.
- **GIS Integration:** The use of Geographic Information Systems to analyze and visualize the spatial data.
- **Outputs:** The generation of various actionable insights, such as (near) real-time dashboards and 3D models, and linking to stakeholder data lakes for further processing.
- **Feedback Loop:** The crucial final step where the insights inform decision-making, which can then be used to modify the physical environment, creating a continuous feedback loop.

Data Ingestion and Digital Twin Core

The process begins with Data Acquisition, where information is gathered from various sources, including environmental sensors, infrastructure systems, and geospatial data storage systems. These data are then processed through an Ingestion stage.

The core of the system is the Digital Twin Core. It incorporates a "Model Creator and Simulation" component that integrates diverse data, including 3D urban morphology, satellite-derived surface characteristics, and environmental sensor data, to capture and model dynamic urban heat processes. Machine learning models, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and gradient-boosted trees, are a key part of this core. They are trained to predict surface temperature distributions using remote sensing indices, land-use configurations, and meteorological inputs.

Fig. 1. Conceptual City-based Digital Twin (Source: The 4th User eXchange during ESA's Living Planet Symposium 2025 poster, Dool, et al. [4])

Scenario Analysis and Feedback Loop

The model is used to introduce various Nature-based Solutions scenarios, such as urban greening, green roofs, and permeable surfaces, to assess their mitigation potential.

Through GIS Integration and advanced analytics, the model generates actionable insights. These insights are presented through outputs like real-time dashboards and 3D models. The final step is the Feedback Loop, where these insights inform decision-making, which can lead to modifications in the physical environment. This creates a continuous cycle of analysis and improvement, supporting data-driven urban planning.

3. Case Study

The research focuses on the application of Destination Earth (DestinE) services to model and analyze Urban Heat Island effects at the city level within an extreme climate context. DestinE is an open platform, and the region of interest could be any location globally. However, to describe the effects on urban infrastructure, the method would work best in an area already experiencing extreme climate changes. The three selected cities, Riyadh, Jeddah, and Dhahran/Dammam, in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA), have distinct local climate profiles, making them excellent candidates for model result comparisons. Also, the cities developed differently over time, adding an extra layer of complexity.

Riyadh: Riyadh is the primary target city for this study due to its extreme climate, characterised by extremely hot summers and limited rainfall. It is also one of the fastest-growing cities in the KSA. This rapid development, combined with the city's arid climate, makes it a crucial location to study the Urban Heat Island effect. The project's alignment with **Saudi Vision 2030** [5, 6] adds significant relevance, as it addresses national development priorities.

Jeddah: Jeddah differs from Riyadh's inland, dry climate because, as a coastal city, it is influenced by humidity and sea breezes. These factors play a key role in the development of urban heat islands. Including Jeddah in the study enables a broader comparison of UHI effects across different urban and climatic contexts in Saudi Arabia. Sea breezes can alleviate the UHI effect by bringing cooler air inland, improving temperatures and human comfort. Additionally, the UHI in Jeddah can drive sea breeze formation, creating a feedback loop that affects the local climate.

Dhahran/Dammam: The Dhahran/Dammam area features a humid-hot desert climate, which poses challenges for industrial and urban sustainability. This climate, marked by extreme heat and high humidity, complicates efforts to address urban heat islands. The region hosts several industrial cities that align with Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030 strategy for economic diversification and sustainable urban development.

Neighborhood Selection: In each city, specific neighborhoods will be chosen to test heat risk mitigation strategies based on their urban morphologies and land use patterns, which are essential for studying urban heat island effects. For example, a high-density area in Riyadh may have extensive impervious surfaces, while a coastal neighborhood in Jeddah could benefit from sea breezes. The Dhahran/Dammam area might include both residential and industrial zones.

This method ensures that solutions are contextually relevant and based on traditional climate-adaptive urban design. Historical data, such as blueprints and land-use maps, further support the study by showcasing the long-term urban evolution and local context of each city.

The platform is conceptualized (under current development) to deliver actionable insights like a reduction of surface temperature near critical infrastructure by 3-5°C, providing (traditional) natural shaded markets, and incorporating the scenario results into new developments to improve their resilience to extreme heat and humidity.

4. Preliminary Results & Analysis

The preliminary results of this study serve as proof of concept to establish baseline values for urban heat in a real-world context. The analysis focuses on a representative neighborhood in Riyadh, the primary target city, due to its extreme climate and rapid urbanization. The provided image (Figure 2) offers a visual example of the urban heat island effect across three cities, displaying a heat map that clearly delineates areas of high temperature. Downtown Dammam and Jeddah are less visible than Riyadh's downtown area due to the heat-sink effects of the Red Sea (Jeddah) and the Persian Gulf (Dammam)

To assess the severity of UHI intensity, we analyzed Landsat 8 surface temperature data from 2020 to 2024 using the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform [7, 8]. Urban areas were identified with Dynamic World land cover data, while rural reference zones were defined by masking non-urban, non-bare pixels within a 30 km buffer around the city (Figure 2). The annual UHI intensity was computed using median summer temperatures to determine the difference between urban and rural surface temperatures. This process generated pixel-level spatial patterns and classified UHI intensity levels from weak to extreme, enabling the identification of thermal hotspots (Dool, et al.).

This initial workflow is a crucial step for future integration into the Destination Earth (DestinE) platform. The ultimate goal is to replicate and scale this analysis across DestinE's ecosystem, enabling interactive digital twins with advanced simulation, visualization, and scenario testing capabilities for effective urban heat mitigation.

The project's next phase will use a digital twin model to simulate the UHI effect and assess the mitigation potential of various **Nature-based Solutions (NbS)**, such as urban greening, green roofs, and permeable surfaces [9]. Our preliminary experiments

introducing green patches in urban areas suggest that targeted NbS interventions can significantly reduce UHI hotspots in high-density areas. The study found that measures such as adding green spaces or installing shaded boulevards can reduce surface temperatures by a noticeable margin.

Fig. 2. Identifying cold (and hot) spots in Damman, Jeddah, Riyadh between 2020 and 2024 using Landsat Land Surface Temperature

These initial findings lay the groundwork for a more detailed analysis and demonstrate the practical value of the DestinE digital twin framework for informing data-driven decision-making in climate resilience planning. By establishing these baseline values, the research provides a foundation for future scenario analysis that can be applied to other cities and regions.

The methodology for this advanced stage incorporates several key strategies:

- **Edge-to-Space Sensing:** This involves integrating IoT, in situ sensors, and satellite Earth Observation data to create a comprehensive picture of the urban environment.
- **Data Fusion Core:** A core system will harmonize real-time and historical data to provide urban climate intelligence.
- **Climate-Aware Modelling:** This process builds on the DestinE Marketplace by incorporating existing data and models.
- **DestinE Integration:** The framework aligns with the Digital Twin Earth platform to enable scalable, policy-driven simulations.
- **Smart Decision Support:** Visual analytics and alerts will power mitigation and planning strategies.

5. Discussion & Conclusion

This research offers key insights into the practical application of digital twin frameworks, such as DestinE, and their potential to revolutionize urban climate resilience strategies. In the initial stages of the project, we made three key observations.

First, we demonstrated that the city-scale digital twin, powered by a system like DestinE, could be a powerful and essential tool for understanding and addressing the complex challenges of Urban Heat Islands. It allows planning to move beyond traditional static analysis by providing a dynamic, data-driven environment for predicting and mitigating the effects of extreme heat in urban areas.

Second, the preliminary results from Riyadh successfully validate the methodology for establishing baseline urban heat values and identifying hotspots, providing a crucial proof of concept for the framework. This demonstrates the framework's scalability and applicability to other cities, underscoring its broader relevance for global urban planning and climate resilience.

Finally, the study's initial findings highlight the significant potential of Nature-based Solutions to reduce urban temperatures and mitigate UHI effects. By enabling the simulation of various NbS scenarios, the digital twin framework provides city planners with actionable insights to inform decisions and create more sustainable, livable urban environments..

6. Outlook

The current research serves as the conceptualization of a business idea aimed at making the Urban Heat Island risk manageable at the city level by providing tangible mitigation and adaptive solutions. The project is currently in a **conceptual stage**, with the existing framework acting as a prototype. The full implementation of the model in Riyadh and two other cities is currently under exploration. To achieve effective **model calibration**, the project requires establishing local data partnerships to adapt the models to specific urban microclimates. The team is also engaged in ongoing work to ensure **platform integration** and align the framework with the broader DestinE infrastructure and its modelling services. The **project's future scalability roadmap targets replicability of the framework across** diverse urban settings. A key component of this effort is **stakeholder engagement**, with plans to co-develop tools directly with urban planners and policy actors to ensure the solutions are both practical and impactful.

Project Objectives:

- Research: Deliver a published white paper (Q4-2025) that explores the foundations of Digital Twinning and its role in translating urban environmental data into actionable policy, with a focus on mitigating urban heat island effects; poster presentation at the AGU-2025.

- Development: Following the publication, design and document a modular Digital Twin architecture (blueprint) that city stakeholders can adapt to assess the feasibility and benefits of UHI mitigation strategies.

Acknowledgments. This project is an internal collaboration within Astra Terra with external partners and is not funded by third-party grants or other financial contributions at this stage.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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